

IMPROVEMENT OF MECHANISMS TO STIMULATE THE PREPARATION OF TEENAGERS FOR SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL LIFE IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *The article reflects on the tasks of improving propaganda mechanisms in preparing teenage youth for socio-spiritual life in families, as well as on the role of mental education of teenage children in family education. It is also mentioned that the initial task in this regard is the involvement by the parents in activities that help improve imagination, perception, thinking, memory and attention, based on the knowledge of the child's interests and needs.*

Keywords: *propaganda, mental education of teenage children, imagination, improvement, perception, thinking, memory.*

There are different approaches to education for young people in the world, and there are specific directions of education in our country. Fundamentally reforming the education system, raising it to the level of modern requirements, training highly educated personnel, educating a perfect personality, educating people who contribute to the development of the Motherland, who have a sense of patriotism and national pride, has become a priority of state policy. Because the main goal of our state is to build a free and prosperous, free and prosperous life, we certainly rely on a comprehensively developed young generation.

In order to contribute to the development of the country in the world, it is important for our youth to incorporate such features as their national language, traditions, culture, and spirituality. Today, scientific researches are being carried out on the formation of national identity among young people, such as national pride, national pride, patriotism, national culture and spirituality in families.

In our country, large-scale reforms on the support of adolescents in the political, socio-spiritual and cultural spheres of social life, the practical situation of propaganda technologies in the socio-spiritual upbringing of adolescents in families, national-spiritual heritage, in particular, folk oral creativity, national traditions, rituals and traditions are also reflected in the development of specific aspects of national education. At the same time, it is one of the urgent tasks to strengthen the moral norms of the characteristics of kindness and affection in social life, its importance in family relations. This creates the need to study the peculiarities of the education and upbringing of teenagers in families in the context of national values, to clarify the system of social and spiritual qualities in them, to improve the promotion technologies based on the family, neighborhood and community cluster in the development of these qualities.

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On State Policy Regarding Youth”, Decree of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PD-4947 “On the Strategy of Actions for Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, Presidential Decree PD-5106 “Effectiveness of State Policy Regarding Youth” dated July 5, 2017, Presidential Decree PD-3907 “On measures to raise morally, morally and physically perfect young people, and raise the quality of their education system to a new level” dated August 14, 2018. This research work serves to a

certain extent the implementation of the tasks defined in the decisions of and other regulatory legal documents.

It is impossible to deny the works of our great thinkers in terms of knowledge and education for the development of the young generation. That is why they recognized the expediency of widely using the views of great thinkers such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Alisher Navai on the education of a perfect person in life.

Scientific research on the issues of preparing young people for family life and spiritual and moral education M.Mahmudova, O.Musurmonova, V.Karimova, A.Munavvarov, M.Kuronov, G.Shoumarov, M.Inomova, D.Rozieva, M. It was carried out by M.Ochilov, N.Egamberdieva, Z.Ismoilova, O.Jamoldinova, Sh.Shodmonova, U.Otanov, G.Izbullaev.

A lot of research has been done by CIS scientists to study this problem. First of all, E.G.Logunova, M.N.Krasnova, L.A.Shvachkina can be mentioned here.

The phenomenon of kindness and the problems of compassion in the system of socio-spiritual values from the scientists of foreign countries, from Western scientists M.Scheler, A.Adler, A.Camus, E.Fromm, I.V. In the scientific works of Goethe², as well as in the dissertation research works of L.Sarolin, I.I.Kurdie, K.Legge, K.A.Layous, the issues of the phenomenon of love were reflected³.

Tasks of improving propaganda mechanisms in preparing adolescents for social and spiritual life in families:

- to determine the pedagogical and psychological conditions for the development of socio-pedagogical promotion technologies in the socio-spiritual education of teenagers;

- development of a model for the development of social and moral promotion technologies for teenagers;

- improvement of the criteria for determining the effectiveness of technologies of socio-spiritual promotion of teenagers;

- improvement of didactic provision of development of socio-pedagogical propaganda technologies in socio-spiritual upbringing of teenagers.

The content, principles, stages, methods and means of developing a sense of national pride in families and the integration of social and spiritual education in families consist of the process of socialization.

The novelty of improving propaganda mechanisms in preparing adolescents for social and spiritual life in families:

- Pedagogical-psychological conditions for the development of social-pedagogical promotion technologies in the socio-spiritual upbringing of adolescents are clarified by optimizing the psychotechnologies based on cooperation in the activity of social institutions in preventive periodicity;

- the model for the development of technologies of socio-spiritual promotion of teenagers has been improved on the basis of the use of “Lifeline”, “Social bridge”, “Safety morophon” technologies of the feedback effect in social-spiritual education in an environment that stabilizes the moderation of the individual in a general action attitude;

- the criteria for determining the effectiveness of socio-spiritual propaganda technologies have been improved based on the adaptation of the complex of personal-reflexive actions that systematically manifest local, young, professional characteristics at the level of individual personalization;

- the didactic support for the development of socio-pedagogical propaganda technologies in the socio-spiritual education of adolescents is improved based on the use of polysensory (seeing, hearing, performing) tools that prevent family conflicts and pathological situations in the person in the impulse of authority status.

The practical significance of the results is that the results of the research can be used in the implementation of cultural and educational measures among the population in neighborhood families, citizens' gatherings, district (city) "Spirituality and Enlightenment" centers, state and public organizations, educational and methodological manuals for general secondary educational institutions. can be used in preparation.

Family is what elevates the honor of nations to a higher rank. In a healthy family, healthy children are born, and patriotic young people, selfless future generations who will contribute to the development of the country, the necessary personnel for the society and the country, will be brought up and grow up. A family is initially built on the love of two people for each other.

In the family, a child is born, bringing joy to the hearts, surrounded by sweet dreams. A son or a daughter is a great blessing given by God. As a girl grows up, the first toy she plays with is a doll. When children play together, one of them is the father, and the other is the mother, and the toys are their children. Maybe that's why the concept of family is embedded in our blood from childhood. That is why the Uzbek people consider the family sacred. In fact, while observing the lifestyle of other peoples, positive qualities such as love for the family, selflessness, sense of the sanctity of the family, responsibility and attitude towards the education of children, harmony in the family, patience, contentment, honesty, and integrity are unique to the Uzbek people. , it seems suitable for Uzbek families. Yes, family is part of society. A strong family is a strong society. If we compare the family to a huge tree, its strong body and roots are father and mother. The branches of such a tree will be healthy and beautiful.

Mental upbringing of teenage children is also important in family upbringing. The primary task in this regard is to engage the child in activities that help to improve imagination, perception, thinking, memory and attention based on seeing the interests and needs of the child. It is also necessary to be able to arouse the child's interest in certain directions and to develop it. In this regard, parents' or other family members' outlook, scope of needs and interests, and the example set by them serve as an educational factor.

Moral education is the core of family education. The goal of moral education organized in the family is to develop the highest moral qualities in adolescents: love for parents and other family members, as well as for others, respect for adults, kindness to children, humility, truthfulness, hard work, generosity, humanitarianism, justice, conscience, etc. - it consists in the formation of honor, pride, discipline, awareness of social duty, etc.

The standard of family life largely depends on the state of the family budget. Therefore, it is advisable to save material funds created by the labor of family members and use them wisely. This allows children to be taught to deal with money from a young age, to get used to a responsible approach to their own and family members' belongings, as well as to the property of family members. To explain to children that money is the value paid for human labor and that it should be used for the most important needs of the family would have a positive effect on their economic education. Economic education organized in the family plays an important role in developing economic literacy and economic thinking in children. The example of parents and adult members of the family has a great educational impact on the formation of economic thinking in children.

Among the conversations organized in the family environment, conversations on legal topics are particularly noteworthy. Legal articles, broadcasts, as well as popular legal literature and discussions on the ideas presented in the media, bring to the attention of the population, lead to the development of legal imagination, perception, thinking, literacy, activity, responsibility, faith and potential in children. In the family environment, giving children information about their responsibilities and, in turn, showing them how to exercise their rights can have good results in this regard.

The family is considered a special place that creates feelings of patriotism and humanity in children. Children first learn the essence of the concepts “Motherland”, “People” in this place. After all, the family itself is a part of the Motherland. Protecting the honor of the family, caring for its preservation, and achieving the integral connection with the feelings of fighting for the honor of the motherland and the good of the country should be the basis of the socio-political education organized in the family.

As mentioned above, the worldviews, life approaches and spiritual world of parents and other family members play a special role in the upbringing of a perfect person. It is also important that parents have a certain level of pedagogical knowledge. The main idea of cooperation between family and educational institutions is to provide pedagogical support for parents. The child also gets used to basic education and skills to follow social norms in the family. Because in the organization of family-social relations: in particular, cultural-household, economic-financial, property relations and work activities, children participate in the process of these relations without realizing it, without understanding its essence, so they collide with social relations, as a result of this type of communication, constant, creates social objective conditions that help parents and children to understand their rights, duties, obligations and responsibilities so that they can be repeated in short periods of time.

From this point of view, it is necessary to determine the public possibilities of the family-educational institution, which was formed historically, taking into account the national and legal features, and to use them effectively.

A number of activities will be carried out to determine the possibilities of family education for educating children and forming their spiritual culture. In this regard, it is possible to cite as an example of the activities carried out with parents:

Work with parents:

a) Interviews with parents.

Interviews are conducted individually and collectively. During the first interview, it is possible to conduct questionnaires that help to determine the level of social awareness and activity of parents and children, which is a guarantee of the success of educating students in a spiritual way, establishing a spiritual culture in them. Questionnaires are of two types, the first of which describes the general portrait of each student, has a diagnostic description, and the second type of questionnaire serves to establish the social education of parents, to determine their personal relationship to the formation of children's spiritual culture.

The analysis of the results of the initial interview and the questionnaires filled out by the parents determines the direction and content of the activities organized with them.

After all, it will be possible to ensure mutual help, kindness, harmony and mutual cooperation between people only in an environment where peace and harmony are ensured.

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